

CARBON EMISSION ASSESSMENT REPORT

Deliverable D2.11

CARBON EMISSION ASSESSMENT REPORT

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.11

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Executive Summary

The healthcare sector is responsible for almost 5% of global greenhouse gas emissions and has a carbon footprint equivalent to 514 coal-fired power plants. If the sector were a country, it would be the fifth largest polluter on Earth. This executive summary provides an overview of the carbon emissions assessment for eight (8) healthcare facilities in Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe. The assessment aimed to understand the carbon emissions in these countries' healthcare facilities and guide mitigation interventions. Post intervention monitoring of carbon emissions will be a crucial aspect of sustainability efforts.

Carbon Emissions Assessment:

Accurate estimation of carbon emissions is essential for healthcare facilities to understand their environmental impact and identify areas for improvement. It serves as a baseline for establishing carbon reduction targets, implementing effective mitigation strategies, and monitoring emissions over time. However, the lack of comprehensive carbon footprint data, especially in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), poses a significant barrier to informed decision-making and targeted interventions. The carbon emissions assessment focused on eight healthcare facilities in Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe. It aimed to quantify and understand the carbon emissions associated with these facilities' operations. The assessment covered various sources of emissions from scope 1 to scope 3, including but not limited to energy consumption, waste management, transportation, and procurement.

Findings:

The assessment revealed varying levels of carbon emissions across the three countries' healthcare sectors. Kenya reported higher emissions, attributed to the larger size of its private healthcare facilities and the diversity of services offered, alongside comprehensive data collection being a public health facility. Public health facilities in Zimbabwe showed moderate emissions, influenced by reliance

on fossil fuels for energy generation, and inefficient transportation systems. South Africa presented lower emission figures for the quarter reported, which may not fully represent the annual trend due to the recent initiation of the study July 2023 and the consequent limited data collection scope. Delays in South Africa were primarily due to delays in obtaining ethics approval.

Mitigation Interventions:

There is evidence of various mitigation interventions in LMICs that aim to address climate change and its impact on health. Due to limited financial resources, a tool called CARBOMICA was developed to guide the allocation of funds towards a package of locally appropriate carbon mitigation interventions in low- and middle-income countries. CARBOMICA employs a systematic approach, considering the potential carbon reduction impact, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility of each intervention. By utilizing this tool, healthcare facilities can prioritize interventions that offer the greatest carbon reduction per unit of investment, optimizing the utilisation of available funds.

Based on the carbon emissions assessments, specific mitigation interventions were recommended for each country. In Zimbabwe, priority interventions focused on transitioning to cleaner energy sources, improving waste management infrastructure, and promoting energy efficiency measures. Kenya's interventions emphasized reduction of emissions from electricity through energy efficient lighting and cooling equipment and renewable energy adoption, optimizing waste management practices, and upgrading of cooling systems to reduce refrigerant emissions. For South Africa, the recommended interventions are shaped by the initial findings and the need for a more expansive data collection. Strategies include initiating comprehensive carbon emissions data collection to identify key areas for improvement, increasing the use of renewable energy based on a detailed understanding of current energy consumption patterns, and exploring circular economy approaches for waste management. Additionally, there is a push

to explore sustainable transportation options that could be more widely implemented once a full emissions profile is established.

Monitoring Carbon Emissions:

Monitoring carbon emissions is of paramount importance to track the impact of mitigation interventions on carbon emissions (and potential co-benefits) and ensure the effectiveness of sustainability efforts in healthcare facilities. Robust monitoring mechanisms, such as regular data collection, reporting, and analysis, are essential for identifying areas of improvement, assessing the impact of implemented measures, and informing future decision-making. A combination of stakeholders; who include the facility managers; and Environmental Health and Safety Teams, need to work together to assess and monitor carbon emissions in healthcare facilities.

Challenges & Opportunities:

The assessment of carbon emissions in healthcare facilities presents challenges due to the complex emissions profile, lack of standardized methodologies, limited awareness and expertise, and financial constraints. However, opportunities lie in improved data collection and monitoring, collaboration and knowledge sharing, technological innovations, regulatory support, and incentives, as well as the alignment of sustainability efforts with improved patient outcomes. By overcoming these challenges and leveraging the opportunities, healthcare facilities can contribute to reducing carbon footprints, promoting sustainability, and enhancing patient care.

Conclusion:

The carbon emissions assessments demonstrate the carbon emissions profiles of eight healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe, Kenya, and South Africa. The recommendations for mitigation interventions, guided by CARBOMICA's resource allocation tool, provide a strategic and cost-effective approach to address emissions. Emphasizing the need for monitoring carbon emissions ensures

ongoing progress towards sustainability goals and fosters a culture of continuous improvement in healthcare facilities. By implementing these recommendations and monitoring progress, healthcare facilities can contribute significantly to reducing carbon emissions and advancing environmental sustainability in the healthcare sector.

Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition/Description
AKDN	Aga Khan Development Network
AKHS	Aga Khan Health Services (Kenya)
CARBOMICA	Carbon Mitigation Intervention in healthcare facilities (a modelling tool designed to facilitate optimised resource allocation on carbon mitigation interventions)
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CHC	Community health centre
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HIC	High-Income Country
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LMIC	Lower Middle-Income Country
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal and Child Health
NCD	Non-communicable disease
TAHMO	Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory
TB	Tuberculosis
UGent	Ghent University (Belgium)
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UK	United Kingdom
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)
Wits RHI	Wits Reproductive Health and HIV Institute (South Africa)

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the report

The purpose of this carbon assessment report is to quantify and understand the carbon emissions associated with private and public healthcare facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. The report highlights the importance of conducting carbon assessments in healthcare settings, supported by relevant sources and citations.

The assessments aim to provide valuable insights into the environmental impact of these facilities. We additionally developed a modelling tool, CARBOMICA, which assists in the strategic allocation of resources to optimize the reduction of carbon emissions at these health facilities. By identifying the key sources of carbon emissions and recommending targeted mitigation measures using CARBOMICA, the report seeks to support the transition towards sustainable and low-carbon healthcare systems in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC).

This report is linked to two other HIGH Horizons reports:

- *Protocol for mitigation interventions evaluation in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe* (Deliverable 5.7, April 2023), which outlines the approach and tools for assessing and evaluating carbon emissions from health facilities in Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe;
- *Development of a Resource Allocation Tool for Carbon Mitigation Intervention in HealthCare Facilities (CARBOMICA)* (Deliverable 3.7, September 2023), which will support the identification and selection of mitigation interventions in the three countries.

1.2 Variation to the project proposal

This deliverable is subject to differences from the original HIGH Horizons works plan. Originally this report was due before the end of April 2023, but because the data from the Kenyan health facilities were pending validation till Autumn 2023

and carbon emission measurements in the South African health facilities started later due to the need for ethics approval, the finalisation of this report was delayed till end of 2023. In the meantime, the HIGH Horizons team started to develop the tool for modelling of alternative mitigation interventions, which is described in deliverable D3.7 of September 2023 “Development of a Resource Allocation Tool for Carbon Mitigation Intervention in HealthCare Facilities (CARBOMICA)”.

2 Background

❖ Need for Carbon Emissions Assessment in the Health Sector

Healthcare facilities have a significant carbon footprint, primarily due to energy consumption, waste generation, and transportation. Healthcare systems contribute approximately 4.4% (1) of global greenhouse gas emissions, underscoring the importance of addressing carbon emissions in healthcare facilities to mitigate their environmental impact and monitoring the progress to reduce emissions (2).

Carbon emissions are linked to climate change, which causes global temperatures to pose significant risks to human health, including heat-related illnesses, the spread of infectious diseases, worsened air quality and adverse mental health outcomes (3). It is crucial for healthcare professionals, policymakers and individuals to act to accurately assess, monitor and keep a reliable carbon inventory to mitigate climate change and protect human health.

Assessing carbon emissions in healthcare is crucial for guiding mitigation and adaptation strategies. By quantifying the carbon footprint of healthcare activities, policymakers and healthcare providers can identify areas of high emissions and implement targeted interventions to reduce them. For example, telemedicine solutions utilizing videoconferencing technology have been identified as a potential opportunity for reducing carbon emissions in the healthcare sector by minimizing the need for travel (3).

Accurate measurement of carbon emissions is essential for healthcare facilities to comprehend their environmental impact and identify areas for improvement. It provides a baseline for establishing carbon reduction targets, implementing effective mitigation strategies, and monitoring progress over time. However, comprehensive carbon footprint data, particularly in LMICs, is lacking, impeding informed decision-making and targeted interventions (4).

The lack of comprehensive assessments of carbon emissions in healthcare, particularly in LMICs, is concerning. LMICs face unique challenges in healthcare delivery and may exhibit different patterns of carbon emissions compared to high-income countries (HICs) (4). Addressing this knowledge gap is crucial for understanding and addressing the environmental impact of the healthcare sector.

Moreover, carbon emission assessments in healthcare provide evidence to support climate action. By quantifying the environmental impact of the healthcare sector, policymakers can make informed decisions about resource allocation and implementing policies to reduce carbon emissions. For instance, Sweden's implementation of carbon taxes as part of its climate policy has reduced CO₂ emissions in the transport sector. A study by Kågeson (2017) found that the carbon tax decreased CO₂ emissions from road transport by 11% between 1990 and 2013. Furthermore, the study estimated that the tax reduced approximately 2.8 million tons of CO₂ emissions annually (5). Similarly, understanding the carbon footprint of healthcare systems can inform the development of strategies to promote sustainable practices and reduce emissions (6).

❖ **Importance of Carbon Assessments in Healthcare Facilities**

Carbon assessments play a crucial role in healthcare facilities as they provide a comprehensive understanding of the carbon footprint associated with their operations. The emissions from healthcare facilities, such as our assessment sites, can contribute to climate change through various pathways. These emissions primarily come from energy use, waste management, refrigerants, transportation,

and some specific health services activities such as use of anaesthesia gases and inhalers; and specifically, greenhouse gases produced include carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide. It is estimated that 15% of the waste produced by healthcare operations contains radioactive, dangerous chemicals, or pathogenic substances (7). To prevent climate change and pollution, and to be able to address the ever-increasing and diverse health demands, healthcare facilities must cut waste and integrate renewable energy. Although it is important to measure carbon emissions in health facilities it is worthy to note that there are gaps in measuring the carbon footprint in health facilities.

❖ **Gaps in Carbon Emission Measurements in the Health Sector**

Within the healthcare sector, accurately quantifying carbon emissions can also pose challenges. Some specific gaps and challenges include:

- a) ***Fragmented Data***: Emission data may be dispersed, with several institutions and organisations gathering and disclosing information on their own. Because of this, it could be challenging to provide an accurate and consistent picture of emissions throughout the industry.
- b) ***Lack of Standardisation***: Standardized procedures and methods are lacking for quantifying and disclosing emissions associated with healthcare. This may lead to discrepancies and make it challenging to compare emissions between various healthcare facilities.
- c) ***Scope of Emissions***: It can be difficult to decide how many of the emissions to include in calculations. In addition to direct emissions from their own energy use and waste management procedures, healthcare facilities may also have indirect emissions from patient transportation and supply chains.
- d) ***Limited Data Availability***: It is likely that some healthcare facilities lack the tools or procedures necessary to gather and submit emissions data. This may lead to data gaps and hinder the efficiency of evaluating and monitoring emissions.

Addressing these measurement gaps requires efforts at both the global and sector-specific levels. Governments, international organisations, and healthcare institutions can work together to develop standardised methodologies, improve data collection and reporting systems, and promote transparency and accountability in emission measurement and reporting.

Firstly, carbon assessment helps understand the current and future carbon emissions associated with various activities, sectors, or geographic regions. This information is valuable for adaptation efforts. Carbon assessments provide insights into the sources and magnitudes of emissions, helping identify sectors or activities particularly vulnerable to climate change impacts. This knowledge allows decision-makers to prioritise adaptation measures and allocate resources effectively. Secondly, carbon assessments provide a foundation for resilience planning by informing the development of strategies and actions that reduce vulnerabilities to climate change. For example, understanding emissions from energy use helps identify opportunities for energy efficiency and renewable energy adoption, enhancing resilience and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Carbon assessment is also essential for designing and implementing effective mitigation strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The following are examples of how it will aid the mitigation efforts:

- **Setting Targets and Goals:** Edwards et al. (2014) emphasised that carbon assessments provide a baseline measurement of emissions, enabling the establishment of reduction targets and goals. By quantifying emissions, decision-makers can set ambitious targets aligned with global climate goals, such as the Paris Agreement.
- **Identify Key Emission Sources and Monitor Progress:** Watts et al (8) highlighted that healthcare facilities can identify the primary sources of carbon emissions within their operations through carbon assessments. This information allows for targeted interventions and measures that address specific areas of

concern. Regular carbon assessments allow for tracking progress towards emissions reduction goals. By comparing emissions over time, decision-makers can evaluate mitigation strategies' effectiveness, identify success areas, and adjust where necessary.

- **Identifying Mitigation Opportunities:** (6) Smith et al pointed out that carbon assessments help identify sectors, activities, or processes with high emissions, offering insights into potential mitigation opportunities. This information enables decision-makers to prioritise actions, invest in low-carbon technologies, and implement policies that promote emission reductions.
- **Optimize Resource Allocation:** The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (9) emphasized that healthcare facilities need to allocate funds efficiently with often limited financial resources. Carbon assessments provide insights into the potential carbon reduction impact, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility of different mitigation interventions. This information enables healthcare providers to prioritise actions that offer the most significant environmental benefit per unit of investment.
- **Demonstrate Commitment to Sustainability:** Smith et al (6) highlighted that conducting carbon assessments demonstrates a healthcare facility's commitment to sustainability and responsible environmental stewardship. It allows them to showcase their efforts in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to global climate change mitigation goals.
- **Supporting Policy Development:** (2016) emphasised that carbon assessments provide scientific evidence and data to support the development of effective climate policies and regulations. They help inform decision-makers about the impact of different policy options, facilitating the adoption of measures that can drive significant emissions reductions.

These references provide the necessary support for the information presented regarding the importance of carbon assessment in understanding and addressing carbon emissions in the healthcare sector.

3 Methodology

Carbon emissions in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe were calculated using the Carbon Management Tool developed by the Aga Khan Development Network (AKDN), which offers a comprehensive methodology for measuring carbon emissions within healthcare organisations.

The tool gathers data from all aspects of operations and the supply chain, enabling calculating the carbon footprint over a specified period. This HIGH Horizons project conducted measurements at 8 sites in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe from January 2023 to September 2023.

To ensure data accuracy, the collected information underwent a quality check. Subsequently, the data were analysed to monitor progress and pinpoint areas where emission reduction efforts can be focused. This methodology empowered healthcare organisations to effectively measure and manage their carbon emissions, facilitating their commitment to reducing their environmental impact.

3.1 Scope and Boundaries

The assessment covered a range of healthcare facility types, including private and public hospitals, clinics, and specialised treatment centres.

Geographically, the assessment targeted healthcare facilities in three countries: Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. These countries were purposively selected based on the HIGH Horizons project's objectives and the need to examine carbon emissions in different healthcare contexts. The selection aimed to provide a diverse representation of healthcare systems and geographic locations.

The assessment period spanned nine months for Kenya and Zimbabwe (from January to September 2023) and three months for South Africa (from July to September 2023) and captured variations and trends over time.

It is important to note that while the assessment aimed to be comprehensive, there may be certain limitations and constraints. These could include data availability, reliability, and the practicality of data collection in some healthcare facilities. Also, another limitation is that we selected only a few facilities purposively as our 'representative number of facilities'. In our assessment, we have only private health facilities in Kenya and only public health facilities in South Africa and Zimbabwe. However, every effort was made to minimise these limitations through rigorous data collection and analysis methods.

3.2 Data Collection

The assessment involved collecting data on various aspects of healthcare facility operations contributing to carbon emissions. This included:

1. Energy consumption,
2. Refrigerants,
3. Anaesthesia,
4. Inhalers use,
5. Transportation,
6. Waste management,
7. Water usage, and
8. Procurement practices.

Primary data were collected through interviews with health facility managers, administrators, and clinical personnel. This was achieved through site visits to our respective healthcare facilities. Secondary data were obtained from relevant literature, reports, and databases.

3.2.1 Sources of Emissions Specific to the Healthcare Facility

Under the International Greenhouse Gas Accounting Protocol (GHG protocol) most of the emissions that arise from healthcare facilities are from direct and indirect service delivery and are classified as Scope 1 (occur from sources owned or controlled by an organisation) or Scope 2 (result from the consumption of purchased electricity, heat or steam). In these scopes, the health facility is directly responsible for taking action to reduce these emissions. Scope 3 describes the emissions released by other organisations associated with but not directly involved in operations. They occur in the value chain of an organisation.

Understanding the various sources of carbon emissions is crucial for practical carbon assessment and management strategies. Scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions provide organisations with a comprehensive framework to identify and address their carbon footprint.

Table 1 below provides an overview of the sources specific to healthcare facilities that can contribute to carbon emissions. The table highlights the various sources of emissions that can result from energy consumption within healthcare facilities, vehicle use, travel distances, and the use of specific medical equipment, such as anaesthetic gases and respiratory inhalers. The table also covers emissions resulting from refrigerant gases used in air conditioning and refrigeration systems, water usage, waste disposal, and the travel of vehicles other than those owned by healthcare facilities, such as patient or visitor vehicles. The tool covers three scopes, Scope 1, 2, and 3, which enable a comprehensive evaluation of greenhouse gas emissions, including those from supply chains (see Table 2 for further details). By understanding the sources of emissions and their scope, healthcare facilities can identify areas where they can implement strategies to reduce their carbon footprint and improve their sustainability.

Table 1: Sources of greenhouse gas emissions in health facilities

Sources of emissions	Description
Energy	Energy consumption within healthcare facilities can contribute to emissions from electricity and heating and other sources such as natural gas, propane, and fuel oil
Vehicle Fuel	Using vehicles for healthcare facilities, such as ambulances, delivery vehicles, and staff vehicles, can contribute to emissions
Vehicle Distance	The distance vehicles travel to and from healthcare facilities can also contribute to emissions
Travel Other Vehicles	Emissions from travel by vehicles other than those owned by healthcare facilities, such as patient or visitor vehicles, may also contribute to the overall carbon footprint
Anaesthetic Gases	Anaesthetic gases used in medical procedures are potent greenhouse gases, and their use in healthcare facilities can contribute to emissions
Refrigerant Gases	Refrigerants used in air conditioning systems, refrigerators, and freezers can also contribute to emissions through leaks or improper disposal
Water	Water usage in healthcare facilities can result in emissions through the energy used in treatment, pumping, and heating processes
Waste	Disposing of waste from healthcare facilities can result in emissions from landfills and waste-to-energy processes
Inhalers	Respiratory inhalers in healthcare facilities can also contribute to emissions by producing and disposing of these products
Construction & Maintenance Materials	The materials used in the construction and maintenance of healthcare facilities can contribute to emissions through the production and transportation of these materials
Construction Logistics	The transportation and disposal of waste generated by contractors working in healthcare facilities can also contribute to emissions
Procurement	Procurement of goods and services for the day-to-day operations of healthcare facilities

3.2.2 Variables of interest

To better understand how carbon emissions are calculated in healthcare facilities, it is essential to look at the variables of interest that feed into the calculation. Table 2 provides an overview of the variables that will be collected and converted into CO₂ emissions, such as building ownership, floor area, energy consumption, fuel consumption, vehicle distance, and waste generation. Additionally, details of procurement, construction materials, and logistics for contractors will be recorded, as well as progress made over time on initiatives to reduce carbon

footprint. The table also includes a currency conversion rate, which will convert local currency to a common currency for emission source expenditure analysis. By capturing these variables, healthcare facilities can better understand their carbon footprint and implement strategies to reduce emissions.

Table 2: Variables of interest

Sheet name	Variables collected	Details of measures
Buildings	Name, Ownership, Floor Area	Information about the building's name, ownership (whether it is owned or rented), and the floor area in square meters
Energy	Details of energy consumption	Details of electricity, gas, and steam consumption for heating, cooling, and other purposes in kWh or GJ.
Vehicle Fuel	Details of fuel consumption	Details of fuel consumption for vehicles, in litres or gallons
Vehicle Distance	Details of vehicle distance	Details of the distance travelled by vehicles, in kilometres or miles
Travel Other Vehicles	Details of other vehicle travel	Details of the distance travelled by other modes of transportation, such as trains or aeroplanes, in kilometres or miles
Anaesthetic Gases	Details of anaesthetic gas usage	Details of the quantity and type of anaesthetic gases used, in litres or pounds
Refrigerant Gases	Details of refrigerant gas usage	Details of the quantity and type of refrigerant gases used, in kilograms or pounds
Water	Details of water usage	Details of water consumption for domestic, industrial, and medical purposes in litres or gallons
Waste	Details of waste generation	Details of the type and quantity of waste generated, in kilograms or pounds
Inhalers	Details of inhaler usage	Details of the number and type of inhalers used
Construction Materials	Details of construction materials used	Details of the quantity and type of construction materials used, in kilograms or pounds
Contractor Logistics	Details of contractor logistics	Details of transportation and logistics activities for contractors, in kilometres or miles
Procurement_T2	Details of procurement	Details of procurement for equipment, appliances, and other materials in dollars or local currency

Sheet name	Variables collected	Details of measures
Procurement_T3	Details of procurement	Details of procurement for services, in dollars or local currency
Spend Mapping	Details of expenditures	Details of expenditures for all categories, including salaries, benefits, and other expenses, in dollars or local currency

3.3 AKDN Carbon Management Tool

According to the guidance provided, the AKDN Carbon Management tool emphasizes completing the sheets in a specific order to ensure accurate calculations. It was recommended to start by filling out the 'Cover sheet' and thoroughly read the essential guidance provided on the 'Cover Sheet' tab. The users were instructed to gather relevant data on carbon emissions from all operational aspects and the supply chain of their healthcare organisations. Below is the order of completion to get the carbon emission measurements.

A. Completion of the 'Cover sheet'

Guided by the cell colours, the researchers populate the tool as required. Below is a figure that shows what the tool's cover page looks like.

Figure 1: AKDN health carbon management tool cover page

AKDN Carbon Management Tool

Headings and guidance are marked grey

Input cells are marked pink
(Input cells essential for calculations are in dark pink)

Output cells are marked in green

Additional support on how to use the tool can be found in the associated guide

The AKDN Carbon Management Tool is continually being improved and updated with feedback from its users. For guidance on its use, to share feedback and to access future updates please contact:

healthcarbon@cotprint@akdn.org

All users must commit to acknowledging AKDN and the use of this tool wherever results are shared or published

Step 1 Complete all pink cells on this 'Cover Sheet'. The selecting the appropriate country on this sheet is required to ensure that the carbon calculations on later sheets accurately reflect country specific variables. Only report data for one country and one agency/organisation per workbook.

Step 2 Complete all pink cells on the 'Buildings' sheet, maximum of 30 buildings per workbook. Input the names of all buildings/sites or groups of sites to be reported. Entering floor area data here enables carbon intensity benchmarks to be populated on the 'Building Totals & benchmarking sheet'

Step 3 Complete all pink cells on the 'Supply Chain' sheet, maximum of 30 suppliers per workbook. Input the names of all suppliers of anaesthetic gases, refrigerants, waste, water, inhalers, contractor logistics and construction. You may not need to complete every sheet. Use the 'Narrative' box at the top of each sheet to explain any significant changes since the last report. Inputting your organisations spending data on the Procurement sheets will enable you to estimate the carbon emissions in your supply chain. With this you can identify carbon hotspots and priority suppliers to engage. To avoid common errors:
1. Avoid copying and pasting data or text into the sheets. If you do, paste as 'values only'.
2. When drop down menus are available they must be used
3. Do not change the names entered for buildings once you have started to complete the sheets.

Step 4 Complete/update relevant pink cells on the 'Actions Tracker' sheet to highlight key actions that are currently underway or planned.

Details of reporting organisation

Agency/Organisation name: _____

Country: Algeria **Note: Only report data for one country per workbook**

Region (in country): _____

Reporting Period (months): Start: _____ End: _____

Date Prepared: _____

Name of person preparing report: _____

Phone number: _____

Cover Sheet | Changes since last version | \$ Conversion | Totals | Supply Chain Totals | Buildi ...

B. Completion of the 'Buildings' sheet

All of the building details of each healthcare facility were recorded in this sheet.

a) Completion of the 'Resource' use sheets.

Before completing the resource use sheets, the researchers familiarised themselves to understand the nature of the data required. There are 11 resource use sheets, as highlighted below:

1) Energy

- Table 1: Grid-supplied electricity.
- Table 2: Renewable electricity generated.
- Table 3: Grid-supplied gas.
- Table 4: Gas cylinders or tanks
- Table 5: Solid fuel
- Table 6: Liquid fuel

2) Vehicle fuel

3) Vehicle distance

4) Travel by other vehicles.

5) Anaesthetic gases

6) Refrigerant gases

7) Water

8) Waste

9) Construction materials

10) Contractor logistics

11) Procurement

3.3.1 Carbon Measurements by Scopes

The tool is built on the accounting premise of 'Financial Control', i.e., emissions are only classed as Scope 1, which relates to an asset on a health facility's balance sheet. This means emissions arising from leased or rented vehicles and rented property are classed as Scope 3.

The tool covers three scopes, Scope 1, 2, and 3, which enable a comprehensive evaluation of greenhouse gas emissions, including those from supply chains (Table 3). The tool can handle specific emissions from the health sector, such as anaesthetic gases, respiratory inhalers, and emissions from energy, transport, waste, and refrigerants. The tool automatically calculates carbon footprints and assigns emissions scopes, providing instant carbon read-outs and diagnostic dashboards that can be used to identify emissions hotspots. This methodology is deemed the most appropriate for trend analysis and will provide valuable information on the effectiveness of mitigation measures over time.

Table 3: Defining scopes of the AKDN health carbon management tool

Emissions scope	Definition	Example
Scope 1	Direct emissions from the organisation's activity	Burning fuel or waste on the premises, using anaesthetic gases, emissions from company vehicles
Scope 2	Indirect emissions from energy consumed by the organisation	Buying and consuming electricity, steam, heat, or cooling from local authorities, emissions from purchased fuels, such as natural gas for heating
Scope 3	Indirect emissions from products or services used to support the organisation's operations	Purchased goods and services, waste disposal, employee commuting, business travel, investments, leased assets, transportation of goods and services

3.3.2 Action Tracker Sheet and Four Data Output Sheets

The tool calculates the carbon footprint for all data provided and automatically assigns emissions scopes. It converts input data into instant carbon read-outs and

diagnostic dashboards. Emissions outputs appear on each line, and totals appear at the top of each sheet as a sheet is completed. Four separate sheets (Error checking; Totals; Supply Chain Totals; Building Totals, & Benchmarking) provide dashboards and charts to help consolidate and interrogate the data. These include a high-level summary and per m² facility benchmarking to help identify hotspots at a facility and an organisation level (10).

3.3.3 Data Quality Scores

The data collection involves gathering information on the type and quantity of resources used. A data quality score can be assigned for each line item to ensure accuracy. The data source is selected from a drop-down list, such as 'from supplier's bills' or 'estimates', contributing to an overall data quality score. This score considers the number of resources used and the level of quality assigned for each line item.

In addition, users can input the unit cost of resources, which will be helpful when prioritising and justifying investments in carbon reduction strategies. The carbon emissions calculated for each line item, including the carbon factor used, the emissions produced, and the GHG protocol scope, are all featured on the sheet. Emission hotspots are identified through a colour ranking system, with red indicating the highest emissions and green the lowest.

3.4 Data Analysis

For our carbon emission assessment, the collected data were analysed using appropriate statistical and analytical techniques. This involved aggregating and organising the data, identifying trends and patterns, and calculating carbon emissions for each emission source and healthcare facility. The analysed data were interpreted to derive meaningful insights and conclusions. The findings were presented clearly and concisely in the carbon assessment report. The report

included graphical representations, tables, and charts to facilitate understanding and communicating the results.

One-way sensitivity analysis was applied to carbon emission data to assess the impact of uncertainties and variations on management decisions by varying a single parameter while keeping all others constant to understand its impact on the outcome. For our carbon emission data, this involved analysing the effects of changing energy consumption patterns or utilisation levels on the overall carbon footprint. By identifying the key drivers of carbon emissions, organisations can prioritise efforts and focus on areas that yield the most significant reductions.

3.5 Carbon Measurement Monitoring Plan

The following monitoring plan outlines a comprehensive framework for continuously measuring carbon emissions in healthcare facilities for the next phase to support emissions reduction efforts and ensure environmental sustainability within the healthcare sector. By implementing robust monitoring methods, evaluating measurement procedures, providing training and capacity building, and establishing systematic reporting and communication practices, healthcare facilities can effectively track and manage their carbon emissions.

3.5.1 Objective

The objective of the monitoring plan is to continuously measure and track carbon emissions in healthcare facilities to support emissions reduction efforts and ensure environmental sustainability.

3.5.2 Scope and Coverage

This monitoring plan encompasses a broad scope, including targeted healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe, South Africa, Kenya, and potentially beyond, depending on the availability and feasibility of monitoring sources. The plan aims to cover various healthcare facilities within these regions, such as hospitals, clinics, and medical centres.

3.5.3 Training and Capacity Building

Training healthcare facility staff on measuring carbon emissions will be an integral part of the monitoring process. The training programme will focus on enhancing the knowledge and skills of the staff involved in the monitoring process. It will cover various aspects, including the proper use of monitoring equipment, data collection procedures, and quality control measures.

The training programme will emphasise the importance of carbon emission monitoring, highlighting its role in sustainability efforts and the significance of accurate data for informed decision-making. Through workshops, seminars, and practical exercises, staff will learn how to use monitoring equipment effectively, follow standardised data collection protocols, and ensure quality control measures are in place. The training programme will also foster a culture of sustainability and environmental awareness among staff.

Regular evaluation and feedback mechanisms are implemented to assess the effectiveness of the training program. This will help identify areas for improvement and provide ongoing support and additional training as needed.

3.5.4 Reporting and Communication

The monitoring plan includes a comprehensive communication strategy to share measurement results with relevant stakeholders effectively. It establishes a reporting framework with defined frequencies and formats, including regular and annual sustainability reports. The plan emphasises timeliness, consistency, and transparency in communication to keep stakeholders informed, involved, and motivated in sustainability efforts. By implementing this communication strategy, healthcare facilities can ensure effective dissemination of measurement data, foster stakeholder engagement, and enhance accountability and transparency in their carbon emission monitoring efforts.

4 Study Sites

4.1 Kenya Sites Description

4.1.1 Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa, and Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi

The assessments are (continuously) taking place in two healthcare facilities in Kenya: the Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa, which serves as the secondary care field site, and the Aga Khan Medical Centre in Kilifi, the primary field site (Figure 2). The regions of Mombasa and Kilifi have a tropical climate, with temperatures ranging from 21°C to 32°C and average annual rainfall ranging from 300mm to 1200mm (11). These areas experience seasonal changes in precipitation and temperatures, which could affect the spread of infectious diseases (12). Both sites offer maternal, newborn, and child health (MNCH) services staffed by qualified personnel, including obstetrician-gynaecologists, midwives, ward and outpatient nurses, and paediatrician consultants. The patient volume at the sites for the past six months has been steady, with an average of 50 daily visits to the outpatient department and 600 admissions per month.

Figure 2: Maps of the location of the Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa

4.2 South Africa Sites Description

In South Africa, the assessments are conducted in an urban setting characterised by a subtropical climate with dry winters and hot summers in Tshwane, located near Johannesburg in Gauteng Province (13) (Figure 3). The region has experienced an increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as heatwaves, droughts, and heavy rainfall due to climate change (14). The closest TAHMO weather station is TA00244 Midrand Fire Station, Cedar Road, Broadacres, with an average annual rainfall total of 657 mm (15). The World Bank Income Group (GDP per capita) for Tshwane is an upper-middle income group of \$6,994 (16). Three maternity facilities in the study area offer various healthcare services, including emergency care, maternal and child health, treatment for acute and chronic diseases, and primary health services, such as dental and reproductive health, mental health, and social services. Pregnant women residing in Urban Heat Islands, where concrete and steel structures absorb and retain heat, have limited means of reducing heat exposure during a heatwave, and health facilities, poorly built brick dwellings and informal housing in urban slums offer little to no protection against heat exposure (17).

Figure 3: Maps of the location of the hospital and CHCs in South Africa

4.2.1 Laudium Community Health Centre

The Laudium Community Health Centre (CHC) is located in Pretoria West and serves approximately 245,387 individuals (18). The facility offers a comprehensive array of health services, including emergency care, maternal and child health, treatment for acute, chronic, and non-communicable diseases, primary health services such as dental care, reproductive health, mental health, and social services, as well as rehabilitation services such as audiology, speech, and hearing (19).

4.2.2 Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre

The Mamelodi District Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre are in region 4, East of Tshwane, which covers an area of 49.19 km² (18). Stanza Bopape CHC serves a population of 261,989 and offers essential healthcare services such as peer counselling, a crisis centre for gender-based violence and sexual assault victims, antiretroviral therapy adherence clubs, COVID-19 screening, and home delivery of medication (19).

4.2.3 Mamelodi District Hospital

Mamelodi District Hospital is a referral centre for patients needing higher-level care, including pregnant women with obstetric emergencies. The hospital has a catchment population of 334,577. It offers clinical specialties in medicine, surgery, obstetrics, paediatrics, psychiatry, radiology, emergency medical services, trauma, and clinical management of NCDs, HIV/AIDS, and TB (20), (21).

4.3 Zimbabwe Sites Description

The study is being conducted in a rural setting characterised by a humid subtropical climate with dry winters and hot summers: Mount Darwin District, located in Mashonaland Central Province (24), (25) (Figure 4). The average annual highest temperature is 33.3°C (91.9°F) (26) [20], and the yearly temperature is 24.6°C (76.3°F) (25) 1.9% higher than Zimbabwe's averages. Mount Darwin typically

receives about 126 mm of precipitation annually, and the area is projected to become drier over time (25). The World Bank Income group (GDP per capita) for Mount Darwin is a lower-middle income group of \$1,737 (27).

Figure 4: Maps of the location of the hospital and CHCs in Zimbabwe

Three public health facilities in the study area provide primary care and referral services, including antenatal care, outpatient and inpatient services, and maternity care. The population in the district mainly survives with subsistence farming and artisanal gold mining, and the health facilities serve a catchment population of approximately 240,000 people (28). The maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births is high, with 462 maternal deaths recorded, and the lifetime risk of maternal death is 1 in 53 (29). Pregnant women have limited means of reducing heat exposure during a heatwave, and even drinking water may be scarce. Pregnant women have limited means of reducing heat exposure during a heatwave, and even drinking water may be inadequate (30). The maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births is high, with 462 maternal deaths recorded, and the lifetime risk of maternal death is 1 in 53 (29). Pregnant women have limited means of reducing heat exposure during a heatwave, and even drinking water may be scarce.

4.3.1 Mt Darwin District Hospital

Mt. Darwin District Hospital is the district's primary care and referral facility. Various services are offered, including curative, preventative, maternity, postnatal, inpatient, outpatient, male and female wards, theatre, laboratory, and pharmacy (31). The average number of women attending antenatal visits in the first month is 164 180, and the average number of deliveries per year is 2295.

4.3.2 Dotito Rural Health Centre

Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic is a primary care clinic 28 kilometres from Mt. Darwin District Hospital. It offers services that include curative (chronic condition screening, monitoring and follow-up, TB screening, initiation, and management), maternity-related services (antenatal care, booking follow-up visit, delivery), postnatal care (visual inspection with acetic acid and cervicography for cancer) and lastly outpatient and inpatient related services. On a monthly average, the hospital services about 80 patients in the outpatient department. The maternity ward has a monthly average of 25-30 deliveries and a yearly average of 292 deliveries.

4.3.3 Chitse Rural Health Centre

Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic is situated 18 km from Mt. Darwin Hospital. The clinic offers services similar to Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic. Services offered include curative, maternity-related services, postnatal care, outpatient and inpatient-related services. There are 18-20 monthly deliveries and about 230 deliveries yearly.

5 Results

A carbon emission inventory comprehensively assesses greenhouse gas emissions generated by an organisation or a specific sector. In the case of healthcare facilities, a carbon emissions inventory would provide an overview of the facility's carbon footprint and help identify areas where emissions reduction

strategies can be implemented. Below is the carbon emission inventory for Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

Notes:

- The total emissions for each facility are the sum of reported emissions across all scopes.
- The data are consolidated over three (3) months as Quarter 1 (January-March), Quarter 2 (April-June) and Quarter 3 (July-September) for the year 2023 for Kenya and Zimbabwe. South Africa data are for three months only (for July-September); hence, it is presented on a monthly basis.
- Only variables with reported data are included. Variables such as Grid Gas, Solid Fuel, and Heat Networks, which had no reported data, have been omitted.
- Procurement data are incomplete across Zimbabwe and South Africa and hence omitted from the service delivery (operations) data.
- "n/a" and dashes indicate no data or not applicable data and have been excluded.

5.1 Kenya Sites

Data collection was done for the period January to September 2023. Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa, has recorded 6,515,262 Kg CO₂ emissions on service delivery activities, with significant contributions from waste, grid electricity, bottled gas, inhalers, and vehicle fuel. Service delivery emissions exclude procurement which corresponds to a total omission of 5,920,147 Kg CO₂ emissions.

The Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi shows a total emission of 6,231 Kg of CO₂, with notable emissions from grid electricity, business travel, and waste.

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected **Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa** encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories as below in Table 4.

Table 4: Emission inventory, Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa

Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)		
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	56,998	52,533	48,427
Scope 1	Bottled gas (LPG)	11,390	15,690	13,521
Scope 1	Liquid fuel (Petrol or Diesel)	1,793	3,172	2,924
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel (Owned Vehicles)	3,021	2,615	3,198
Scope 3	Business travel (Taxi, Car hires, Train, Air travel or local bus)	9,963	22,304	13,205
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	12,201	11,731	12,672
Scope 1	Refrigerants	14,717	49,832	4,540
Scope 3	Waste	66,696	63,027	56,660
Scope 3	Inhalers	13,329	14,655	14,300
	Total Emissions from Operations (Kg CO₂)	1,889,622	2,589,853	2,035,787
Scope 3	Procurement	1,699,513	2,354,293	1,866,341

From above data for the Aga Khan Hospital, wastes contribute 31% of service delivery emissions with electricity at 27%, followed by refrigerants (12%), bottled gas and inhalers at 7.0 % respectively and anaesthesia gas (6%). (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Total emissions, Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi** encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 5.

Table 5: Emission inventory, Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi

Aga Khan Medical Centre-Kilifi		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)		
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	764	1,717	447
Scope 3	Business travel (Taxi, Car hires, Train, Air travel or local bus)	365	122	365
Scope 3	Waste	866	810	775
	Total Kg CO₂	1,995	2,649	1,587

The Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi data covered only three variables, with electricity contributing 47% of emissions, followed by waste at 39% and business travel at 14% (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Total emissions, Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi

5.2 South Africa Sites

This report presents an initial analysis of carbon emissions data from three healthcare facilities in South Africa for the period July to September 2023: Laudium Community Health Centre, Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre, and Mamelodi Regional Hospital. The data cover a range of emission sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories.

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Laudium Community Health Centre**, encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 6.

Table 6: Emission inventory, Laudium Community Health Centre

Laudium Community Health Centre		July	August	September	Q3 Totals
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)			
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	21,450.91	17,209.44	8,171.77	46,832.12
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	4,979.22	12,120.47	16,711.83	33,811.52
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	-	1,430.69	1,758.63	3,189.32
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	1,687.23	-	-	1,687.23
Scope 3	Business travel	167.46	246.78	5,024.86	5,439.10
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Refrigerants	5,746.74	5,746.74	5,746.74	17,240.23
Scope 3	Waste	8,479.37	7,969.99	4,454.26	20,903.62
Scope 3	Inhalers	7,921.05	5,825.54	10,227.74	23,974.34
Total Kg CO₂		50,431.99	50,549.66	52,095.84	153,077.49

Laudium Community Health Centre recorded total emissions of 153,078 Kg CO₂. The primary contributors to these emissions were grid electricity (31%), liquid fuel (22%), and inhalers (16%). Other significant sources included waste (14%) and refrigerants (11%) (Figure 7). Vehicle fuel consumption data in September is being queried with the fleet manager.

Figure 7: Proportional Breakdown of Carbon Emissions by Source, Laudium Community Health Centre for Q3 2023

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre**, encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 7.

Table 7: Emission inventory, Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre

Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre		July 2023	August 2023	September 2023	Q3 2023 Totals
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)			
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	-	4,100.82	5,379.23	9,480.04
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	2,096.51	6,551.60	6,206.78	14,854.90
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	38,896.46	38,137.11	994.61	78,028.18
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	-	-	-	-
Scope 3	Business travel	34.49	34.56	1,660.77	1,729.82
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Refrigerants	1,937.92	1,937.92	1,937.92	5,813.77
Scope 3	Waste	726.98	807.21	1,196.46	2,730.65
Scope 3	Inhalers	22,115.75	4,220.70	10,566.54	112,637.36
	Total Kg CO₂	65,808.11	55,789.92	27,942.31	149,540.34

Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre reported emissions totalling 149,540 Kg CO₂. Most of these emissions came from inhalers, accounting for 50% of the total, followed by vehicle fuel (35%). Other sources included liquid fuel (7%), grid electricity (4%), and refrigerants (2%) (Figure 8). Interestingly, inhaler prescriptions are reported to be considerably higher during the winter months, as well as being linked to respiratory disorders from a nearby mining operation.

Figure 8: Proportional Breakdown of Carbon Emissions by Source, Stanza Bopape Health Centre for Q3 2023

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Mamelodi Regional Hospital**, encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 8.

Table 8: Emission inventory, Mamelodi Regional Hospital

Mamelodi Regional Hospital		July 2023	August 2023	September 2023	Q2 2023 Totals
CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)					
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	65,600.31	3,105.17	1,868.75	70,574.23
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	-	-	-	-
Scope 3	Business travel	60,761.32	60,761.32	3,038.07	124,560.70
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	1,494.60	1,494.60	-	2,989.20
Scope 1	Refrigerants	22,899.74	22,899.74	22,899.74	68,699.23
Scope 3	Waste	15,905.82	15,041.99	15,515.42	46,463.23
Scope 3	Inhalers	1,873.84	14,247.59	11,076.93	27,198.36
	Total Kg CO₂	168,535.63	117,550.41	54,398.91	340,484.95

Mamelodi Regional Hospital showed total emissions of 340,484 Kg CO₂ (Table 8). The leading source of emissions was business travel, constituting 36% of the total. This was followed by vehicle fuel (21%), refrigerants (20%), waste (14%), and inhalers (8%) (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Proportional Breakdown of Carbon Emissions by Source, Mamelodi Regional Hospital for Q3 2023

5.3 Zimbabwe Sites

This report presents a preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from three health facilities in Zimbabwe in the period January to September 2023: Mt Darwin District Hospital, Chitse Rural Health Centre, and Dotito Rural Health Centre. The data encompass various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories.

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Mt. Darwin District Hospital**, encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 9.

Table 9: Emission inventory, Mt. Darwin District Hospital

Mt Darwin Hospital		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)		
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	23,288.87	12,649.24	5,219.91
Scope 1	Grid gas	-	-	0.29
Scope 1	Bottled gas (LPG)	55.85	799.17	1,205.11
Scope 1	Liquid fuel (Petrol or Diesel)	904.12	1,117.22	1,514.73
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel (Owned Vehicles)	11,560.44	16,306.15	15,957.47
Scope 3	Business travel (Taxi, Car hires, Train, Air travel or local bus)	47.42	66.57	54.92
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	1,526.94	1,526.94	1,064.89
Scope 1	Refrigerants	-	-	-
Scope 3	Waste	1,251.17	1,101.15	1,678.13
Scope 3	Inhalers	1,153.68	1,184.04	1,146.09
	Total Kg CO₂	39,788.49	34,750.49	27,841.54
Scope 3	Procurement	7,051.46	12,151.39	12,366.82
	Total Kg CO₂	46,839.95	46,901.88	40,208.36

From Mt Darwin District Hospital data, electricity and vehicle fuel contributes 31 % of service delivery emissions respectively, followed by waste at 4%, anaesthesia gas at 3% and inhalers at 3.0 % respectively (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Proportional Breakdown of Carbon Emissions by Source, Mt. Darwin District Hospital for Q1-Q3 2023

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Chitse Rural Health Centre**, encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 10.

Table 10: Emission inventory, Chitse Rural Health Centre

Chitse Rural Health Centre		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)		
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	8,443.92	5,098.96	272.88
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	-	-	-
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	974.54	377.16	55.57
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	-	34.43	23.44
Scope 3	Business travel	467.77	184.30	6.46
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	-	-	-
Scope 1	Refrigerants	-	6.00	-
Scope 3	Waste	184.09	150.86	204.67
Scope 3	Inhalers	-	379.50	493.35
Total Kg CO ₂		10,100.48	6,231.21	1,101.11

The data from **Chitse Rural Health Centre** show electricity contributes 95% of total emissions followed by waste and bottled gas at 4% and 1% respectively (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Proportional Breakdown of Carbon Emissions by Source, Chitse Rural Health Centre for Q1-Q3 2023

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from **Dotito Rural Health Centre**, encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 11.

Table 11: Emission inventory, Dotito Rural Health Centre

Dotito District Council Hospital		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
		CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)		
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	6,749.78	-	2,771.74
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	-	-	-
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	728.14	-	358.94
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	-	51.63	22.14
Scope 3	Business travel	1,717.58	51.15	42.52
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	-	-	-
Scope 1	Refrigerants	-	-	-
Scope 3	Waste	218.21	221.90	329.83
Scope 3	Inhalers	-	1,510.60	464.80
Total Kg CO₂		9,443.11	1,835.28	3,990.40

The data from **Dotito Rural Health Centre** show electricity contributes 83% of total emissions followed by waste and vehicle fuel at 16% and 1% respectively (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Proportional Breakdown of Carbon Emissions by Source, Dotito Rural Health Centre for Q1-Q3 2023

6 Key Findings

The data indicate variability in the sources and volumes of emissions across the facilities.

- Scope 1 emissions, particularly from refrigerants, vehicle fuels, and liquid fuels, are a typical high contributor across the sites.
- Scope 2 emissions, particularly from grid electricity, are the highest contributor across the sites.
- Scope 3 emissions also represent a significant portion, especially from business travel, waste, and Inhalers.
- There are gaps in the data where emissions are not recorded or understated (indicated by "-") or not applicable ("n/a"), which may impact the accuracy of the emissions profile for each facility.

The assessment revealed varying levels of carbon emissions across the three countries' healthcare sectors (Table 12).

Table 12: Carbon emissions across three countries

Country	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)		
	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
Kenya	1,891,617.02	2,592,501.11	2,037,374.28
Zimbabwe	66,383.54	54,968.38	45,299.87
South Africa	No data collected	No data collected	643,102.78

From January to September 2023, Kenya reported higher emissions, attributed to the larger size of its private healthcare facilities and the diversity of services offered, alongside comprehensive data collection. In contrast, Zimbabwe's emissions were moderate, largely due to data collection on a limited number of variables. The limited scope of data collected can partly explain South Africa's lower emissions figures for the third quarter, as the project faced delays in obtaining ethics approval, thereby impacting the study's comprehensiveness in these sites. Kenya exhibited higher emissions due to the comprehensive and

consistent data collection, the size of healthcare facilities, the diversity of services offered in the healthcare facilities and the size of the facilities.

6.1 Comparative Country Analysis

The carbon emissions data from South Africa, Kenya, and Zimbabwe provide a comprehensive overview of the healthcare sector's impact on the environment within these regions. A cross-comparison of the data highlights several key points:

6.1.1 Kenya

The data from Kenyan sites span from Q2 2021 to Q3 2023 (with Q1 2021-Q4 2022 provided as Annex 1), indicating a structured and continuous data collection process that can reveal trends over time.

The emissions are detailed quarterly, allowing for observing seasonal variations and the impact of specific interventions or events.

Total emissions figures for each quarter suggest a progressive approach to monitoring, with the potential for implementing mid-year adjustments based on half-yearly performance.

6.1.2 Zimbabwe

Zimbabwe has reported their data monthly (Annex 2) and seem to focus more on Mt. Darwin, as shown in the detailed breakdown by site.

Notably, the Mt. Darwin Hospital and Chitse Health Centre have highlighted areas where emissions are significantly higher, such as business travel and anaesthetic gases, which could be targeted for reduction strategies.

In Dotito District Council most data are missing or very low, suggesting that it may be an area with exceptionally low emissions or a focus for detailed data collection.

6.1.3 South Africa vs. Kenya and Zimbabwe

The South African sites have reported their data monthly, which may provide more immediate feedback on changes in emissions but for now lacks the longitudinal depth of the Kenyan data.

South African facilities show diverse emission sources with significant contributions from Scope 1 emissions, like the Kenyan and Zimbabwean data.

The Kenyan and Zimbabwean data appear to be more comprehensive, covering a broader time frame, which could provide a better understanding of the effectiveness of any interventions.

6.2 Cross-Regional Insights

A regional comparison reveals common challenges, such as managing Scope 1 emissions, predominantly from vehicle fuel and anaesthetic gases.

Business travel appears to significantly contribute to Scope 3 emissions across all regions, highlighting a potential area for region-wide improvements, such as adopting teleconferencing or more efficient travel planning.

In all regions, there are gaps in the data where emissions are not recorded or not applicable, indicating room for improvement in data collection methodologies.

6.3 Recommendations for Cross-Regional Collaboration

1. Leverage the extended data collection period from the Kenyan sites to set benchmarks for other regions, including South Africa and Zimbabwe.
2. Share best practices and insights across African regions, particularly regarding managing high-emission areas.
3. Consider a unified reporting framework to facilitate direct comparisons and regional analysis.

4. Encourage knowledge exchange programs to address specific challenges, such as reducing anaesthetic gas emissions.

6.4 Recommendations for HIGH Horizons

1. Standardize data collection methods to ensure consistency and completeness across all sites.
2. Investigate the high-emissions sources for potential reduction strategies, particularly in Scope 1.
3. Perform a cross-regional analysis with Kenyan, South African and Zimbabwean data to benchmark and share best practices.

7 Way Forward

7.1 Carbon Mitigation in Healthcare Facilities

Based on the carbon assessment findings, specific mitigation interventions were recommended for each country.

- Kenya's interventions emphasized emissions reduction from electricity through energy-efficient lighting and cooling equipment and renewable energy adoption, optimizing waste management practices, and upgrading cooling systems to reduce refrigerant emissions.
- South Africa's interventions centered around further advancing renewable energy infrastructure, implementing circular economy principles in waste management, and promoting sustainable transportation alternatives.
- In Zimbabwe, priority interventions focused on transitioning to cleaner energy sources, improving waste management infrastructure and processes, and promoting energy efficiency measures especially for Mt Darwin Hospital.

7.2 Resource Allocation using CARBOMICA

The resource allocation tool CARBOMICA was developed to guide the allocation of funds towards mitigation interventions. The development of CARBOMICA is described in deliverable D3.7 of September 2023 “Development of a Resource Allocation Tool for Carbon Mitigation Intervention in HealthCare Facilities (CARBOMICA)”. CARBOMICA employs a systematic approach, considering each intervention's potential carbon reduction impact, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility. By utilising this tool, healthcare facilities can prioritise interventions that offer the most significant carbon reduction per unit of investment, optimising the utilisation of available funds. HIGH Horizons will further finetune the CARBOMICA tool and deploy it to model and identify mitigation interventions that will be implemented and evaluated in the selected health facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe from Spring 2024 onwards.

7.3 Challenges and Opportunities

Monitoring carbon emissions is paramount to tracking the progress of mitigation interventions and ensuring the effectiveness of sustainability efforts in healthcare facilities. Robust monitoring mechanisms, such as regular data collection, reporting, and analysis, are essential for identifying areas of improvement, assessing the impact of implemented measures, and informing future decision-making.

The assessment of carbon emissions in healthcare facilities presents challenges due to the complex emissions profile, lack of standardised methodologies, limited awareness and expertise, and financial constraints. However, opportunities lie in improved data collection and monitoring, collaboration and knowledge sharing, technological innovations, regulatory support, incentives, and aligning sustainability efforts with improved patient outcomes. By overcoming these challenges and leveraging the opportunities, healthcare facilities can contribute to reducing carbon footprints, promoting sustainability, and enhancing patient care.

8 Conclusion

This report describes the carbon emissions measured in health facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe in 2023 and has identified pivotal challenges in assessing carbon emissions in these healthcare facilities. Key among these is the complex nature of emission sources, lack of standardised assessment methodologies, limited expertise in carbon management, and financial constraints. These challenges highlight the need for a nuanced approach to accurately categorise and assess healthcare sector emissions.

Conversely, these challenges present significant opportunities for improvement and innovation. Enhanced data collection and analysis can lead to more accurate emission profiles. Collaborative initiatives can foster knowledge sharing and the development of innovative solutions. Technological advancements promise more efficient practices and supportive policies and incentives can encourage emission reduction efforts. Significantly, aligning these initiatives to improve patient care adds a vital dimension to these efforts.

The findings from our carbon assessment of healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe, Kenya, and South Africa are integral to this discussion. The strategic and cost-effective mitigation interventions recommended by CARBOMICA's tool are crucial for addressing these emissions. Continuous monitoring of carbon emissions is essential to track progress towards sustainability goals and to encourage a culture of ongoing improvement in healthcare facilities.

In conclusion, by addressing these challenges and harnessing these opportunities, healthcare facilities can significantly reduce their carbon footprint, foster sustainability, and enhance patient care. The implementation of these recommendations, coupled with diligent monitoring, positions healthcare facilities to make meaningful contributions to environmental sustainability in the sector.

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Annex 1. Quarterly Kenya Data from Q1 2021 to Q3 2023

Building/site	Q1-2021	Q2-2021	Q3-2021	Q4-2021	Q1-2022	Q2-2022	Q3-2022	Q4-2022	Q1-2023	Q2-2023	Q3-2023
Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa	CO2-e (metric tonnes)										
Scope 2 Grid Electricity	60,614	58,815	54,914	65,679	65,249	58,049	50,154	59,856	56,998	52,533	48,427
Scope 1 Bottled gas(LPG)	9,038	8,010	8,706	11,280	11,978	13,557	11,684	11,792	11,390	15,690	13,521
Scope 1 Liquid fuel(Petrol or Diesel)	1,655	3,945	1,159	965	965	497	-	2,978	1,793	3,172	2,924
Scope 1 Vehicle Fuel (Owned Vehicles)	2,502	2,340	2,665	3,098	3,131	2,462	2,969	2,612	3,021	2,615	3,198
Scope 3 Business travel (Taxi,Car hires, Train, Airtravel or loc	1,405	1,111	5,021	1,328	5,613	4,645	6,840	11,217	9,963	22,304	13,205
Scope 1 Anaesthetic gases	53,941	101,369	13,568	13,756	13,050	11,213	12,015	16,303	12,201	11,731	12,672
Scope 1 Refrigerants	56,794	148,408	60,245	8,671	10,544	43,222	24,010	3,734	14,717	49,832	4,540
Scope 3 Waste	63,038	74,669	83,344	72,299	76,420	73,855	73,809	73,084	66,696	63,027	56,660
Scope 3 Inhalers	10,089	13,188	5,357	4,291	11,622	13,576	9,520	11,647	13,329	14,655	14,300
Total Kg CO2	259,076	411,855	234,979	181,367	198,573	221,076	191,001	193,224	190,109	235,559	169,446
Scope 3 Procurement	2,561,903	2,501,001	3,124,355	3,008,935	2,561,903	2,509,229	2,367,346	2,816,885	1,699,513	2,354,293	1,866,341
Total Kg CO2	2,820,979	2,912,856	3,359,334	3,190,302	2,760,476	2,730,305	2,558,347	3,010,109	1,889,622	2,589,853	2,035,787
	Q1-2020	Q2-2020	Q3-2020	Q4-2020	Q1-2021	Q2-2021	Q3-2021	Q4-2021	Q1-2023	Q2-2023	Q3-2023
Aga Khan Medical Centre-Kilifi	CO2-e (metric tonnes)										
Scope 2 Grid Electricity	1,274	987	558	967	-	405	-	1,081	764	1,717	447
Scope 3 Business travel (Taxi,Car hires, Train, Airtravel or loc	365	365	365	365	365	365	365	365	365	122	365
Scope 3 Waste	1,108	753	759	833	999	810	-	614	866	810	775
Total Kg CO2	2,748	2,106	1,682	2,166	1,364	1,581	365	2,061	1,995	2,649	1,587

Annex 2: Monthly Zimbabwe Data from Q1 2023 to Q3 2023

Mt Darwin Hospital										
	Building/site	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September
		CO2-e (metric tonn								
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	11,328.86	4,401.27	7,558.74	-	11,328.86	1,320.38	748.22	792.23	3,679.46
Scope 1	Grid gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.29
Scope 1	Bottled gas(LPG)	-	-	55.85	-	64.35	734.82	440.89	382.11	382.11
Scope 1	Liquid fuel(Petrol or	314.48	275.17	314.48	331.03	314.48	471.72	524.13	495.30	495.30
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel (Owned	6,153.26	3,743.24	1,663.95	3,025.35	6,153.26	7,127.53	7,127.53	6,176.34	2,653.60
Scope 3	Business travel (Tax	15.64	15.64	16.14	13.95	15.64	36.98	23.62	21.33	9.97
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	508.98	508.98	508.98	508.98	508.98	508.98	555.91	508.98	0
Scope 1	Refrigerants	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Waste	373.40	397.34	480.43	323.03	359.20	418.93	203.41	208.98	1,265.74
Scope 3	Inhalers	387.09	379.50	387.09	455.40	387.09	341.55	394.68	364.32	387.09
	Total Kg CO2	19,081.71	9,721.13	10,985.65	4,657.74	19,131.86	10,960.88	10,018.39	8,949.59	8,873.56
Scope 3	Procurement	1.14	0.95	4.97	4.34	1.14	6.68	6.68	4.37	1.32
	Total Kg CO2	19,082.85	9,722.08	10,990.62	4,662.08	19,133.00	10,967.56	10,025.07	8,953.96	8,874.88
Chitise Rural Health Centre										
	Variable	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	2,399.22	2,640.76	3,403.94	1,056.30	1,643.43	2,399.22	52.82	44.01	176.05
Scope 1	Grid gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Bottled gas	-	15.47	14.70	-	-	-	-	44.09	-
Scope 1	Solid fuel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.22	0.43
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 2	Heat networks	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	210.51	153.83	610.20	-	166.65	210.51	-	-	55.57
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	-	-	-	21.25	13.19	-	8.79	8.79	5.86
Scope 3	Business travel	184.30	99.16	184.30	-	-	184.30	3.23	3.23	-
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Refrigerants	-	-	-	3.00	3.00	-	-	-	-
Scope 3	Waste	53.88	62.86	67.35	35.92	61.06	53.88	63.76	70.96	69.95
Scope 3	Inhalers	-	-	-	379.50	-	-	166.98	136.62	189.75
	Total Kg CO2	2,847.91	2,972.08	4,280.49	1,495.97	1,887.34	2,847.91	295.58	307.92	497.61
Dotito district council										
	Variable	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September
Scope 1	Grid Electricity	2,472.63	1,653.12	2,624.04	-	-	-	2771.74	-	-
Scope 1	Grid gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Bottled gas	14.70	14.70	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Solid fuel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.43
Scope 2	Liquid fuel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 1	Heat networks	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 3	Vehicle Fuel	192.29	228.18	307.66	-	-	-	-	307.66	51.28
Scope 3	Vehicle Distance	-	-	-	18.99	16.32	16.32	16.32	2.91	2.91
Scope 1	Business travel	715.66	429.40	572.53	18.88	7.17	25.1	7.17	35.35	-
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 3	Refrigerants	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scope 3	Waste	61.06	71.84	85.31	67.35	61.06	93.49	104.44	119.61	105.78
Scope 3	Inhalers	-	-	-	581.00	464.8	464.8	464.8	0	0
	Total Kg CO2	3,456.34	2,397.23	3,589.54	686.22	549.35	599.71	3,364.47	465.53	160.40